

Effect of silica on the crystallization behavior and microstructure of mica glass-ceramics in the system $\text{SrO}\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$

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Abstract : The effect of varying the SiO_2 content on the crystallization and microstructural behavior of strontium containing glasses based on the system $\text{SrO}\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$ was investigated by differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

DTA analysis revealed that the glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallization peak temperature (T_p) increased by increasing silica content. It was also shown that the higher the silica content, the lower is the aspect ratio of the fluorophlogopite crystals and appearance of pores in the body. The analysis of X-ray diffraction patterns revealed that strontium fluorophlogopite crystals exist as major phase in all heat treatment temperatures.

Keywords : Glass-ceramics, DTA, X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscope.

Introduction

The glass-ceramics, a polycrystalline material composed of at least one crystalline phase dispersed in a vitreous matrix, is produced by the controlled crystallization of highly viscous glass-forming melts. The transition occurs from 'vitreous to crystalline' in glass-ceramics via two kinds of transformation : nucleation and crystal growth. The first one is an endothermic process and the second one is an exothermic process¹. The two dimensional mica crystals are nucleated internally and crystallized from fluoride containing glasses. The most unique feature of mica glass-ceramics is that they can be machined to precise tolerances and surface finish with conventional metal working tools²⁻⁷. Mica glass-ceramics, particularly phlogopite system, have excellent machinability due to the layered lattice structure of the sheet silicates arranged in a 'house of cards' microstructures, which causes a perfect basal cleavage along the (001) planes of mica crystals. Besides above, they possess higher strength, fracture toughness, thermal shock resistance, and have excellent dielectric properties.

Beall⁷ undertook the first study of the alkaline earth fluoromica glass-ceramics, later on Hoda and Beall^{2,3} investigated glasses of different compositions containing

barium, calcium and strontium based on fluorophlogopite stoichiometry. Most of the compositions were susceptible to crystallization during casting. They also observed that these alkaline earth containing materials have the properties of high mechanical strengths, refractoriness, and in case of strontium containing glass-ceramics, a unique phenomenon of water swelling and self disintegration to clay like particles.

Greene *et al.*⁸ investigated on the alkaline earth containing glass-ceramic system based on (1-Z) BaO : Z K₂O : (6-X) MgO : X MgF₂ : (3-Q) Al₂O₃ : Q B₂O₃ : 8SiO₂ system (where Z=0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0, X=2, 2.5 and 3.0 and Q= 0, 0.5 and 1) and observed that barium substitution by potassium results in increase in molar volume and co-efficient of thermal expansion and reduction in fractional glass compactness, microhardness and glass transition temperature.

Honda *et al.*⁹ studied on a new type of fluorophlogopite, which was formed in the machinable glass-ceramics system $\text{SiO}_2\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot \text{MgO}\cdot \text{Na}_2\text{O}/\text{K}_2\text{O}\cdot \text{F}^-$. They observed that this type of mica 4-5 times more machinable than house of cards types phlogopite glass-ceramics and also reported that phase separation in the base glass took place during nucleation and crystallization through controlled heat treatment.

Gregg *et al.*^{10,11} investigated microstructural development in different compositions based on the system, $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)\text{-Ba}_{0.5}\text{-Mg}_3(\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10})\text{F}_2\text{-Mg}_2\cdot\text{Al}_4\cdot\text{Si}_5\cdot\text{O}_{18}$ as a part of US NIH programme towards developing CAD/CAM dental ceramics.

Henry *et al.*¹² studied nucleation and crystallization behavior based on $8\text{SiO}_2\cdot\text{YAl}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2\cdot\text{BaO}$ where the varying of aluminum oxide ($Y = 1.5\text{--}3.0$). They clearly indicated the reducing the alumina content reduces the glass transition temperature, first peak crystallization temperature and promotes bulk crystal nucleation. The first peak was corresponding to barium fluorophlogopite. High alumina contents favoured the formation of cordierite, mullite and barium aluminum silicate.

Henry *et al.*¹³ investigated microstructure, hardness and machinability based on $8\text{SiO}_2\cdot\text{YAl}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2\cdot\text{BaO}$ with variation of aluminium oxide ($Y = 1.5\text{--}3.0$). They reported that hardness and machinability is highly dependent on the formation of an interconnected house of cards microstructure.

Recently Uno *et al.*^{14,15} prepared glasses from the ternary system $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)\text{-Ba}_{0.5}\text{-Mg}_3(\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10})\text{F}_2\text{-Mg}_2\cdot\text{Al}_4\cdot\text{Si}_5\cdot\text{O}_{18}$. The detail compositions were not given, however it was stated that the compositions were close to $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\cdot\text{Mg}_3(\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10})\text{F}_2$ stoichiometry. They clearly indicated the improvement in strengths and fracture toughness values. They also concluded that barium containing glass-ceramics were 2–3 times more stronger than conventional mica-containing glass-ceramics¹⁴.

In the previous work¹⁶ we have studied the kinetics as well as the crystal growth with respect to fluorine content in the barium fluorophlogopite glass-ceramics based on the system $\text{BaO}\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$, where it was indicated that the crystallization of the glass was largely homogenous and fluorine promotes initial crystallization.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no previous attempt has been made to study the nucleation, crystallization, crystal growth, strength and machinability in strontium fluor mica glass-ceramics compositions by varying the SiO_2 content.

In the present investigation, we have studied the effect of varying silica on the nucleation and crystallization behavior of the glass having the generic composition of $\text{SrO}\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$.

Experimental

Parent glass preparation :

The glass batches with weight-percentage compositions of SrCO_3 , SiO_2 , MgO , Al_2O_3 , MgF_2 and H_3BO_3 based on high purity and analytical grade reagent (E. Merck) were prepared (Table 1). The composition of the batches was selected on the basis of the generic formula

Table 1. Chemical composition of the glass batch as (w/w%)

Batches	SrCO_3	MgO	Al_2O_3	MgF_2	SiO_2	H_3BO_3
S0	15.64	16.79	11.05	14.59	38.50	3.44
S3	15.41	16.54	10.88	14.64	39.08	3.44
S5	15.28	16.41	10.80	14.53	39.53	3.44
S7	15.17	16.29	10.72	14.42	39.97	3.44

$\text{SrO}\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$ in such a fashion that excess SiO_2 was gradually added from 0, 3, 5 and 7% of the silica content of batch S0. Moreover, in all the batches, 2% excess B_2O_3 was added to facilitate melting. Four different glass batches were properly mixed and wet milled in an attrition mill and thereafter the batches were melted in a platinum crucible in an electrically heated furnace with fixed soaking time of 2 h at 1450 °C. The glass melts were occasionally stirred by platinum rod to homogenize melt. The glass melt was then poured into a hot cast iron mould to make the glass block of 55 mm × 30 mm × 10 mm dimension. After development of sufficient strength, the glass block was released from the mould and immediately transferred to an annealing furnace operating at 650 °C and soaked for 1 h followed by natural cooling to room temperature. After annealing, the glass blocks were cut into 2–3 mm thickness pieces with the help of a precision low speed cutting machine (Buehler). A portion of the glass samples were agated ($\sim 75\ \mu\text{m}$) for DTA analysis to find out glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallization peak temperature (T_p).

Heat treatment :

The glass samples were heated to nucleation temperature at the rate of 10 °C/min and kept at the nucleation temperature for 2 h. Subsequently, heated to the corresponding crystallization temperature at the heating rate of 2 °C/min and were kept at this temperature for 5 h to achieve controlled crystal growth.

Characterization techniques :

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) :

Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) was done using

Shimadzu DT40 thermal analyzer with α -alumina powder as reference material. The four different derived glasses were crushed and finally ground to $\sim 75 \mu\text{m}$ suitable for DTA analysis. Non-isothermal experiments were performed by heating $\sim 17 \text{ mg}$ glass sample, crystallized at different temperatures, at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in the temperature range from ambient to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

X-Ray powder diffraction (XRD) :

Four heat treatment temperatures were investigated by X-ray powder diffraction on powder samples. All samples were heat treated using a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$ to the nucleation temperature at $720 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (mentioned earlier), soaked for 2 h at this temperature, heated again at $2^\circ/\text{min}$ to the corresponding crystallization temperature and was kept at the temperature for 5 h followed by natural cooling to room temperature. Powder XRD analysis were performed using X-ray diffractometer (PW 1830, Panalytical) using Ni filter $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$, X-ray radiation at scanning speed of $2^\circ (2\theta)$ per minute. The diffraction patterns were recorded within Bragg angle range $10^\circ < 2\theta < 70^\circ$. The phases were identified by JCPDS numbers (ICDD – PDF2 data base).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) :

Samples from all the crystallization temperature (heating schedule as mentioned earlier) were studied to investigate the microstructural development with secondary electron imaging (SEI) mode in a scanning electron microscope, Hitachi, S3400N, Japan. Before study, surface of all the samples were polished with diamond paste followed by chemical etching with dilute HF solution.

EDX analysis :

EDX analysis was performed to find out chemical composition of crystals formed in ceramised materials. EDX analysis was performed by Thermo Scientific, NORAN-System SIX analyser.

Density :

The densities of all the samples, ceramised at different temperatures, were measured by water displacement method using Archimedes principle.

Results and discussion

Results of differential thermal analysis (DTA) :

DTA curves of the four glass samples at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ are shown in Fig. 1. Only one exothermic

Fig. 1. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) curves of glass samples with variation in SiO_2 content at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

peak was observed in all batches. The glass transition and crystallization temperatures were determined from DTA analysis of the glass samples. The glass transition temperature (T_g) and glass crystallization peak temperature (T_p) shifted to higher temperature as the SiO_2 content was increased. This might be due to the enhanced bridging bonds in the silica-based network leading to an increase in viscosity and elevation of glass transition temperature.

Results of X-ray diffraction (XRD) :

Different crystal phases formed at different crystallization temperatures are identified and presented in Table 2 using JCPDS reference files.

Using the JCPDS reference files used to identify the various crystal phases formed are identified and presented in Table 2. At $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, strontium fluorophlogopite phase appeared as a major phase in the batches S0 and S3 while in S5 and S7 no visible peaks are observed (Figs. 2–5). At $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, strontium fluorophlogopite was present as major

Table 2. List of JCPDS files for identification of the main crystal phase in ceramised glass

Crystal phase	JCPDS reference file
[Strontium fluorophlogopite $\text{Sr}\cdot\text{Mg}_3\cdot\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10}\cdot\text{F}_2$]-SF	00-019-0117
Strontium aluminium silicate $[\text{SrAl}_2\cdot\text{Si}_2\cdot\text{O}_8]$ -SS	00-038-1454
Enstatite $[\text{MgSiO}_3]$ -E	00-002-0546

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of S0 glass samples at different crystallization temperatures [SF-Strontium fluorophlogopite, SS-Strontium aluminum silicate and E-Enstatite].

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of S5 glass samples at different crystallization temperatures [SF-Strontium fluorophlogopite, SS-Strontium aluminum silicate and E-Enstatite].

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of S3 glass samples at different crystallization temperatures [SF-Strontium fluorophlogopite, SS-Strontium aluminum silicate and E-Enstatite].

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of S7 glass samples at different crystallization temperatures [SF-Strontium fluorophlogopite, SS-Strontium aluminum silicate and E-Enstatite].

phase in all the batches except the difference in relative intensity of the peaks. At 1000 °C, ‘strontium fluorophlogopite’ as major phase and ‘strontium aluminium silicate’ as minor phase was identified in all the batches. At 1100 °C, both ‘strontium fluorophlogopite’ and ‘strontium aluminium silicate’ was observed as major phases with almost equal amounts. The presence of small amounts of enstatite is also observed in all the batches. The absence of any crystalline phase at 800 °C in S5 and S7

batches may be attributed to the higher viscosity with increased silica additions. With increasing heat treatment temperature, the formation of strontium aluminium silicate and enstatite is progressively increased. This may be the indication that the formation and stability of strontium fluorophlogopite is favoured at lower temperatures in all the batches. Henry *et al.*^{11,12} also demonstrated similar observation when they prepared machinable barium fluorophlogopite glass-ceramics. It seems that at higher

Fig. 6. EDX analysis of crystalline phases of S0 sample crystallized at 1100 °C.

temperatures, strontium aluminium silicate is formed at the cost of strontium fluorophlogopite.

Results of scanning electron microscope (SEM) :

At 800 °C, liquid-liquid phase separation took place in S0 and S3 but at the same heat treatment temperature, no phase separation was observed in S5 and S7 batches (Figs. 7–10). But with the increase in temperature to 900 °C, some blocky crystals with submicron microstruc-

Fig. 7. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of different glass-ceramic samples nucleated at 720 °C for 2 h and crystallized at 800 °C for 5 h, (A) S0, (B) S3, (C) S5, (D) S7.

Fig. 8. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of different glass-ceramic samples nucleated at 720 °C for 2 h and crystallized at 900 °C for 5 h, (A) S0, (B) S3, (C) S5, (D) S7.

tures were observed in first two batches but only liquid-liquid phase separation took place in the batches with higher silica percentage i.e. in S5 and S7. At 1000 °C, all the four batches showed lath shaped crystals with quite high aspect ratio along with some blocky crystals. Samples, heat treated at 1100 °C, exhibited large crystals having much higher aspect ratio with inter locking microstructure¹⁷. Generally it is also been observed that in all the

Fig. 9. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of different glass-ceramic samples nucleated at 720 °C for 2 h and crystallized at 1000 °C for 5 h, (A) S0, (B) S3, (C) S5, (D) S7.

Fig. 10. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of different glass-ceramics samples nucleated at 720 °C for 2 h and crystallized at 1100 °C for 5, (A) S0, (B) S3, (C) S5, (D) S7.

batches at different crystallization temperatures, pores of different sizes in substantial numbers were present while the size and numbers of the pores increased with temperature as well as with silica additions (Figs. 7–10). This observation corroborates the gradual lowering of densities (Fig. 11) with increase in silica content as well as with increase in temperature.

EDX analysis :

EDX analysis was carried out for S0 sample, heat treated at 1100 °C in scanning electron microscope (Fig. 6). The average chemical composition shows the forma-

Fig. 11. Variation of bulk density of different batches against glass and glass-ceramics samples at different crystallization temperatures.

tion of fluorophlogopite mica crystals in the glass-ceramic material.

Density :

With increase in silica content the density of glass-ceramics samples was increased upto 900 °C (Fig. 11). But beyond this temperature (1000 °C and 1100 °C), density gradually decreased even lower than the glass itself. This might be due to the formation of substantial number of large sized pores at higher crystallization temperatures.

Conclusions

From the above study on the crystallization and microstructural behavior of the glass-ceramic materials based on Sr·Mg₃·Al·Si₃·O₁₀·F₂ mica system, by varying the SiO₂ content in glass composition, it may be concluded that :

- The glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallization temperature (T_p) increases progressively with increase in SiO₂ content in the compositions as evidenced from DTA analysis.
- In all the batches, strontium fluorophlogopite appears as major crystalline phase irrespective of heat treatment temperatures studied.
- Higher amount of SiO₂ generally favours the formation of strontium aluminium silicate at higher temperatures.
- Increasing SiO₂ content, the number and size of pores increases within the materials.

- The aspect ratio of strontium fluorophlogopite crystals increased with increasing heat treatment temperature but with increase in silica content, the crystal growth hinders to some extent which is related to higher viscosity imposed by higher silica content in batches.

Hence it can be concluded that the batch S0 having no extra silica has the best property amongst all batches with respect to microstructural development i.e. 'house of cards' microstructure and the stability of fluorophlogopite phase crystallized at 900 °C.

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